

School Well-Being for Students in the Intergrated Boarding School Tapaktuan City

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Abstract— The purpose of this study was to look at the picture of school well-being among students in the Tapaktuan City boarding school. This study used a survey method of 100 students. Data were collected using a number of questions related to the dimensions of school well-being. The results of this study indicate there are problems with the school well-being of students as seen from the aspects of having, loving, being, and health.

Keywords— Students, school well-being, boarding school.

I. INTRODUCTION

The school is a place of learning environment that provides the best experience for welfare and optimization of student functions (Frost, 2010). In the view of Karyani, et al (2015) students feel prosperous when there is a sense of security, comfort, happiness, peace, and health in the school environment. For a long time, the world health organization, WHO (World Health Organization) has long paid attention to school welfare by increasing the number of schools and assessing each school's characteristics to strengthen its capacity as a healthy environment in life, learning and workplaces (WHO, 1998). According to WHO (1998), school well being is a health concept that focuses on caring for individuals or other groups by creating more conducive school conditions, building the capacity of schools that care socially, peacefully and educatively, and prevent from various diseases. This WHO concept has become the background for the formation of a theoretical model of school well-being based on the concept of sociological well-being (Konu & Rimpela, 2002). Based on these explanations, WHO has hopes to be able to make schools a learning environment that is able to contribute to students as the next generation of an educated and healthy nation.

School well-being is an assessment of students related to the state of the school, both in the form of the physical condition of the school, social relations, the needs of students, and the health of students in the school environment (Konu and Rimpela, 2002). Meanwhile, Dariyo (2018) suggested that school well-being is an assessment of individuals in participating in teaching and learning activities in the school environment to create a pleasant atmosphere for all individuals involved in certain education. Another opinion expressed by YoungMinds (2019) states that school welfare refers to mental health conditions, where each individual is aware of potential, can deal with pressure at school, can work productively and profitably, and is able to contribute to his school.

School well-being is very important for students, especially for boarding-based schools. Tapaktuan City is one

of the cities that has Islamic boarding schools which are of interest to students in the surrounding environment. Many parents flocked to enter their children to boarding schools to increase religious knowledge and get the best service to achieve the future of their children.

Therefore, in this study researchers were interested in seeing the picture of school well-being in students in the City of Tapaktuan.

II. OBJECTIVES & METHODS

The purpose of this study was to look at the picture of school well-being among students in the Tapaktuan City boarding school. This study used a survey method of 100 students.

Data was collected using several questions related to the dimensions of school well-being.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The survey results can be seen as follows:

Based on the survey results, it can be found that there are problems that occur in the Pesantren of Tapaktuan City as follows:

- Learner fatigue with 16% assignments. Some participants mentioned that many tasks were given in a limited amount of time, causing fatigue to occur in students. Rest is not enough to make students experience fatigue.

- b. Bullying with a percentage of 19%. The bullying action that occurs in students is verbal bullying which is more often done by girls such as often mocking possessions of friends, insulting regional origin, often forced by seniors to do something. Whereas physical bullying is mostly done by men such as fighting in a dormitory, often taking friends' belongings in a dormitory, and likes to hit.
- c. The physical condition of the pesantren is still incomplete, which receives a percentage of 38%. The pesantren's target facilities for student complaints are the number of toilets that are too small with a large number of participants. In addition, UKS that was not utilized, the number of damaged computers, noisy environment, and food available in the canteen did not show four healthy five perfect.
- d. The health condition of students with a percentage of 9%. Students are often sick due to consuming unhealthy foods, often experience smallpox, heartburn, and some students are brought home to their parents.
- e. Student achievement has decreased by a percentage of 14%. The decline in student achievement is due to personal problems such as feeling lazy to learn and lack of motivation to study diligently and actively.
- f. Skipping behavior that gets a percentage of 3%. Truant behavior is carried out by boys when there is fatigue learning in boarding schools.
- g. About 1% of students who are forced into a pesantren school by their parents are not on their own.

Based on some of the problems above indicate an alarming phenomenon of school life. These conditions make students feel uncomfortable, and provide negative effects felt by students, this indicates that welfare in schools is still not achieved. As stated by Rahmawati and Abidin (2014) which revealed that the problem of students in schools is caused by the environment in the form of a school context that does not create a healthy atmosphere, where schools should have a comfortable, caring, friendly, and warm atmosphere. But on the contrary, if the availability of good school facilities, the quality of supportive services, and mutual support between students and teachers, in general students assess their school well-being has been fulfilled (Urifa, 2018). Therefore, based on the results of the survey above it is suspected that the welfare of students in the school environment is still relatively low. As the opinion stated by Konu & Lintonen (2006) reveals that the welfare of students becomes low if the students feel that all needs in the school have not been met, whether seen from the condition of schools that are still less supportive, social relations are not good, the needs are not fulfilled and uncontrolled health of students.

IV. CONCLUSION

The survey results show that there are student problems that make them dissatisfied in the school environment. the student's assessment of the school being low can be seen from the physical condition of the school (having), social relations (loving), fulfillment of students obtained from school (being), and the health status of students (health).

V. SUGGESTION

This study uses students who were in junior and senior high school based on integrated boarding school as research participants because of the limitations of researchers. Therefore, if possible, researchers can then consider comparing students who are not based on integrated boarding school as research participants, so that the difference between school well-being in boarding school -based students and those who do not enter boarding school can be seen.

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